

PRODUCTION AND TESTING OF SELECTED CLOTHING ACCESSORIES MADE USING MACRAMÉ AS OFFICE WEARS FOR FEMALE UNIVERSITY STAFF IN NORTH EAST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was on "Production and testing of selected clothing accessories made using macramé for female university staff in North East Nigeria". The main objective of the study was to produce and test some selected clothing accessories made using macramé for female university staff in North East, Nigeria. To guide the study; three objectives and three research questions were formulated. The study was delimited to three universities offering Home Economics in Northeast Nigeria, square knots and larks knots of macramé techniques were used to produce tote bags, slippers, necklaces, earrings and watch straps. Thirty (30) female staff were used to carry out the study, these were selected using the purposeful random sampling techniques. The instrument of data collection was a self-structured assessment card titled "Assessment card for rating of clothing accessories produced using macramé" (ACRCCPUM). The instrument was face and content validated by experts and the reliability was determined using Fleiss kappa. A pilot study was carried out with 4 female staff from the Department of Home Economics, Federal College of Education, Yola and it yielded a reliability coefficient (K) of 0.764, indicating good agreement. The data for the study was collected by the researcher and two research assistants. Thirty assessment cards were given alongside the produced clothing accessories to the 30 models to use; that are academic and non-academic staff and all the 30 assessment cards were collected back after two weeks from the three universities and all were valid, which were subjected to data analysis. The research questions were answered using mean, simple percentage and frequency table. Items with a mean of 75 and above were considered as good per the decision rule. Findings showed that; the clothing accessories produced using Macramé were comfortable with 54.2%, fitted with 87.8% and accepted for use as office wears with 85.8%. It was recommended among others therefore that; female university staff should be encouraged to use clothing accessories made using macramé techniques since they are comfortable, fitting and accepted for use as office wears which will improve their appearance.

Keywords: Clothing Accessories, Macramé, North East, Female Staff, University

INTRODUCTION

The appearance and aesthetic look of an individual has to do with the totality of what the individual is wearing. The items that make up the beauty appearance apart from the garment the individual is wearing, hanging, or holding is referred to as clothing accessories. Clothing accessories are part and parcel of what comes in contact with the body, apart from the garment that is being worn. These clothing accessories serve as decorative items and adornment or beautification which enhances the look of the individual or serves as a compliment to the apparel. A change of clothing accessories makes an impactful difference in the overall appearance of the wearer. According to Hubpages (2021) clothing accessories can completely change the way an individual looks even when the individual is wearing the same garment as was previously

worn. These clothing accessories can be pieces of items, added to the basic clothing to make dressing more meaningful and complete. Clothing accessories, therefore, need to be comfortable, unique, durable, carefully selected, and attractive.

According to Chivers (2024), Clothing accessories provide interest to one's outfit and extends the life of clothes. They add versatility as well as personality to an individual's look and express one's unique personal style. Clothing accessories can serve both functional and ornamental purposes, which are often used to complete an outfit and to compliment the wearer's look. The ornamental purpose can be said to be decorative, enhance aesthetic of an outfit, add colour, texture and visual interest. While the functional purposes are to protect the body from hot weather, insects or harmful objects and weather, Insects or harmful objects and carrying essentials. Examples of clothing accessories include; bags, footwear, belts, jewelries, hats, scarves and many more. For clothing accessories to be fashionable and accepted for use, certain attributes are necessary which include comfort, fitness, texture, and aesthetic appearance. The comfort of any clothing accessories during use is a basic factor or attribute a wearer looks for, how comfortable and convenient the accessories are will determine for how long the wearer can use and wear the accessories. The more fitting an accessory, the more beautiful the accessory is. Clothing accessories which include jewelry, hanging bags, shoes, hats, and many others can be made from different materials such as raffia, metals, plastics, glass, leather, fabric, wire, and other fibers. These accessories come in different sizes and shapes, which are chosen in relation to figure types or shape.

Macramé is an art of using the techniques of knotting to produce useful items; it is an art and craft of decorative knotting without using needles or hooks. It is also believed to be an Arabic word 'magramah' or 'fringe.' Macramé is a type of ornamental work, made by knotting and weaving thread into a pattern to produce items such as; table clothes bed sheets and curtains in most homes in the olden days (Virginia, 2019). Different types of macramé stitches and techniques includes; square knot, spiral technique are used to make ropes, jewelries and belts, hitch techniques, frivolite technique are used on edges of a piece, picot technique, a combination of square knots, spiral method and larks head technique are used to attach pieces together (Jonathan, 2016). Materials for macramé include; cords made of cotton twine, linen, hemp, leather strips, other yarn, fine thread, lace and silk strips. Jewelries made using macramé are often combined with various beads pendants or shells and other decorative stones. It is in this regard the researcher intends to produce some clothing accessories from these creative knots and determine its comfort, fitness and level of acceptability among female university staff. This will help in testing the opinion of these female lecturers that are meant to use these accessories, and to ascertain their level of acceptability. This is very important to this study because it will go a long way to suggest that the clothing accessories produced where accepted by these female lecturers or not. Opinion is a subjective or value judgment, a person's belief, idea or feeling, about something (Mayers & Troolin, 2023)

It is very important therefore, to use a very comfortable, light weighted texture, fitted items suitable for the nature of their job which involve long sitting or standing and moving from one place to another. It is in view of this, that the researchers were motivated to explore the use of macramé technique being an age long hand crafts to produce some selected clothing accessories and determine its comfort, fitness and level of acceptability among female university staff in Northeast Nigeria, when used as office wears.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Macramé technique is an age long crafts that have lasted for many decades but unfortunately, its vogue and popularity in recent times is fading away and going into extinction. One can hardly see clothing accessories that are made from this old craft. Salierno (2022) stated that most women are driven to purchase accessories that are not functional but are stylish in terms

of design and colour. The beauty and uniqueness in terms of the designs and intricate patterns, stitches and knots of these craft that is breathable in nature and allows air circulation and movement, the good fitting makes these clothing accessories comfortable on the wearer which of no doubt, what makes it unique and outstanding. The reintroduction of this craft to produce clothing accessories as substitute making the craft available and popular once more is definitely a good innovation in the fashion world. These craft can be used as a means of entrepreneurial opportunity for the university graduates when properly taught from 100 levels to their final year. After graduation this will serve as an income generation to graduates, make them self-reliant, self-employed and employer of labour.

The climate and hot weather condition in North Eastern region of Nigeria makes the use of most clothing accessories uncomfortable on the wearer because of the materials they are made from. These clothing accessories available are mostly made from synthetic, leather or skin with some parts made from metal or plastic. Examples include; bags, shoes, earrings, neck laces, wrist watches and others. These accessories many at times chops off or peels off over a period of time when used due to hot weather condition, friction with the body during use resulting in wearing and tearing. Willie (2021) had reiterated that bags and shoes made from leather peel and crack in hot weather.

The texture of clothing accessories are affected by the hot weather which in turn makes the skin to react by irritation, rashes, pains or itches depending on the types of clothing accessories a wearer is using and on which part of the body making these accessories uncomfortable on the wearer during use. For example; shoes made from leather and animal skin create an uncomfortable feeling and pains on the toes when used for a long period of time during the day when the weather is hot. Some of these accessories that have some metal parts like the wrist watches, necklaces and earrings bring out some whitish or greenish substance resulting into fading away. These accessories, because of the nature of materials they are made up of when used over a period of time loosen up due to expansion because of the hot weather condition thereby making them free or loose on the wearer when used the next time.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The major objective of this study was to produce and test some selected clothing accessories made using macramé as office wears for female university staff in North East, Nigeria. Some specific objectives include;

1. Ascertain the comfort of clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by university female staff in Northeast, Nigeria.
2. Assess the fitness of clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by university female staff in Northeast, Nigeria.
3. Determine the level of acceptability of clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears for corporate dressing by university female staff in Northeast, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the comfort of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by female University staff in Northeast, Nigeria?
2. What is the fitness of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by female University staff in Northwest, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of acceptance of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique as office wears by female University staff in Northeast, Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPT OF CLOTHING ACCESSORIES

Clothing accessories are items or things which are used as secondary manner besides the wearer outfit, often used to complete an outfit and chosen to specifically complement the wearers look. It can further express an individual's identity and personality as there are accessories that come in different shapes, sizes, hues, (Bowers, 2019). They can be items that are decorative which are matched with clothing, which include ornaments such as; earrings, necklaces, bangles/bracelets, scarves and gloves, hats and carrying items such as; bags according to their way of use. Accessories therefore enhance the effect of clothes an individual wears because it is said to be anything worn or carried, apart from the clothes or apparel worn which adds to beauty and attractiveness of the individual wearing or carrying the item. Accessories further emphasize one's personal styles, taste, and preferences. They are important details needed to complete the look or outfit of an individual.

According to Hasan (2023), accessories are supplementary items that can be added to or worn with a garment to accentuate or complement it. They enhance the aesthetic appearance of an outfit and serve as decorative, functional, and ornamental purposes. These accessories may be made from metal, fabric, cross-link, polymer among others and may vary according to their end use. They are often used to complete an outfit and are chosen to specifically complement the wearer's look. In other word, all other items worn on the body, carried or hang in one part of the body or the other apart from the apparel, are accessories in respective of what material they are made up of. These items complete and enhance or supplement one's aesthetic appearance. They include; jewelries, gloves, handbags, hats, belts, scarves vile, watches, sunglasses, hair pins, stockings, bow ties and likes.

Accessories also add colour, style and class to one's outfit and create certain look which may be practical or functional. Theresa (2017), stated that, accessories has the ability to change the way one looks even when wearing the same apparel. This also means that accessories further express an individual's identity and personality, these accessories come in different shapes, sizes, colours and materials.

TYPES OF ACCESSORIES

There are different types of accessories that are used by individuals; these accessories are classified into two major groups or general areas; those that are carried and those that are worn, (Jonathan, 2016). Accessories that are carried include; handbags, hand fans, umbrellas, wallets and pulse. Those that are worn include; jackets, boots, foot wear sandals, slippers shoes, ties, hats, belts, gloves, ear rings, necklaces, bracelets, watches, eyewear, shawls, scarves, vile, socks, rings, bow ties, hair bow hair pins and stockings.

CONCEPT OF MACRAMÉ

According to Bharti, Saroj and Neelam (2019), macramé is a form of textile-making by series of knots. macramé is a wonderful and delightful craft, through which several useful items can be produce, example include; bags, hanging baskets wall hangers and jewelries. Macramé jewelries is often made in combination of various beads made of glass, wood, pendants or shells. Wilder (2019), viewed macramé as a popular homemade fiber art, which involves tying knots with cotton cord. These knots vary in complexity and there are hundreds of different items that can be produce using macramé technique. Macramé is a form of weaving using knotting techniques to create textiles. A range of things from pot holders, wall hanging to jewelry can be made from macramé. There are six basic macramé knots, from which different varieties can be developed (Popsicle, 2016). These include:

- i. **Larks head Knot;** the larks head knot forms the foundation of many macramé designs.

To make the larks head knot;

Step 1: Fold string in half and drape the halfway point over the rod/cord.

Step 2: Once more fold the string under the red/cord,

Step 3: Bringing the two Centre pieces of string, through the bottom loop, pull tight. (Popsicle, 2016)

ii. **Half knot:** the half knot is often used to create a helix structured knot. The knot twists when repeated.

To make the half knot;

Step 1: Begin with two pieces of string and two larks head knot.

Step 2: Take the outside string from the right hand larks head knot and pass it under the two centre strings, pass this string over the last string on the left.

Step 3: Now move the far left hand strings over the two centre strings and then under the last cord on the right. This completes your half knot. Repeat to desired size.

iii. **Square knot;** the square knots is one of the most common macramé knots and beads can be sandwich in between the knots to make designs and great macramé jewelry. To make the square knot;

step 1: Follow the steps one to three of the half knot.

Step 2: Bring the far right string over the two centre strings and under the far left string.

Step 3: Take the far right string and pass it under the two centre strings, then over the far right string, pulling tight to form the knot. (Popsicle, 2016).

iv. **Overhand knot:** The overhand knot is used at the beginning or end of macramé design, but care need to be taken when using it at the end of a macramé work, so the work does not unravel or loosen up. So to secure the work a little glue is used on the string before the overhand knot is done.

Step 1: Use a single piece of string or multi-strands; take the right hand string over the left forming a loop.

step 2: Move the same string under and through the loop created, finishing on the right, pull to tighten. (Popsicle, 2016).

v. **Single half hitch**; the single half hitch is used for any design, it is great for creating a multi strand weave.

To make the single half hitch;

Step 1: Take a single string, under the rod/cord back over.

Step 2: Bring the same string under the rod cord and over the loop created, pull to tighten.

(Popsicle, 2016).

vi. **Double half hitch**; the double half hitch is like the single half hitch but in a double form, this is a decorative knot that is used in many designs.

To make the double half hitch;

Step 1: Take a single string under the rod/cord then back over.

Step 2: Bring the same string under the rod/cord and over the loop created.

Step 3: Move the bottom string, back over the rod/cord, then under and up through the loop.

Step 4: Pull to tighten, repeat until the desired size.

Macramé Tools/Materials

It is very important to know the different types of cords used in macramé work, as they give different effect to finished work when used. Beads are added to jewelry work as well as other accessories such as bags, shoes, and wall hangers. Macramé as an interesting craft cannot be done using machine but every single knot is done by hand. Measurement is very vital as the require work can only be gotten by the correct length of cord and the kind of cord one chooses (Amopmah, 2015). The basic equipment and tools needed to get started with macramé:

Mounting cords/ dowel, Rings (for mounting cords), Macramé board or project board, pins (T-pins), Scissors, Measuring tape, Embroidery needles, Cords and Crochet hook

Macramé Hang Bag (white and ash coloured tote bags)

Step 1: Mount 100 inches cotton cord using larks head knots at an interval of ½ inch until work measures 30 inches.

Step 2: Using square knots macramé technique, continue to knot until the end of the cords while inserting beads at 2 inches interval.

Step 3 : Finish up the bottom of the bag with back stitches.

Step 4: Using the spiral method, make two bag handle measuring 17 inches.

Step 5: Cut the same measurement of lining fabric and fix a zip.

Step 6: Attach it into the bag and tack well at the two sides.

Macramé Shoe

Step 1: Mount larks head knot unto a cotton cord at $\frac{1}{2}$ an inch interval until it measures 10 inches.

Step 2: Using square larks head knots macramé technique, knot until work measures 10 inches.

Step 3: End the knots.

Step 4: Fix the lining fabric behind the macramé piece.

Step 5: Use gum to fix the piece onto a shoe sole.

The same macramé technique will be used for the two shoes.

Macramé Necklace

Step 1: Using square larks knots, work for 20 inches length inserting beads at half an inch interval on the two 6mm cords.

Step 2: Secure the ends.

Step 3: Fix hooks at the two ends.

Macramé Earrings

Step 1: Using square larks knots work for 4 inches inserting beads of half an inch interval.

Step 2: Fold into two to form a double pattern.

Step 3: Make a loop and fix a hook at the end.

Step 3: Knot to secure the edges on one side with a loop and making a double knot on the other edge to interlock.

Wrist watch strap

Step 1: From a wrist watch remove the tow straps, leaving the hooks fixed.

Step 2: Mount four to eight macramé cords

Step 3 Work on square larks inserting beads at intervals.

Step 4: Secure the ends using hooks

METHODOLOGY

POPULATION FOR THE STUDY

The total population of the study was one thousand three hundred and sixty six (1,366) female staff from three universities offering Home Economics in Northeast, Nigeria. These are made up of twenty-six (26) were Home Economics lecturers and one thousand three hundred and forty (1,340) other female staff both academic and nonacademic working in the universities. Namely; Adamawa state university, Mubi, Modibbo, Adama University, Yola and Taraba State University, Jalingo.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The sample size of the study comprised of thirty (30) models that are made up of all the female university staff in the three universities used for this research. Ten (10) each were selected from each of the university using the systematic

random sampling technique. The clothing accessories were used by each of these selected staff at the same time for two weeks to ascertain the comfort, fitness, and acceptability.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The instrument employed for this study was a self-structured assessment card titled “Assessment card for rating of clothing accessories produced using macramé” (ACRCCPUM).

DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected from the models, were subjected to descriptive statistics such as; frequency table, mean and simple percentage. Data were arranged and analyzed using percentage and mean to determine the comfort, fitness, and level of acceptability of the produced clothing accessories using macramé techniques.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the comfort of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by female University staff in Northeast, Nigeria?

Table 1: Responses on comfort of clothing accessories made using Macramé as office wears dressing. (Hand bags, shoes, necklace, earrings and watchstraps)

S/N	Required Observation	MCA (%)	
		Yes	No
1	Clothing accessories feels light in weight on the wearer during use which gives free movement	102 (68)	48 (32)
2	Clothing accessories are flexible, making it feel loose when used and easy to remove	99 (66)	51 (34)
3	There is feeling of aches and pains on the body during the use of clothing accessories (breathability)	39 (26)	111 (74)
4	Clothing accessories are irritating to the skin when used (allergic reactions)	28 (18.7)	122 (81.3)
	Grand Mean (percentage)	67 (44.7)	83 (55.3)

Clothing accessories produced using macramé techniques when used for office wears by the University staff were not comfortable on the wearer as the total mean score and percentage of 83 and 55.3 percent, respectively. However, items 1 and 2 for crochet and macramé accessories revealed that Yes responses were higher than the No responses as shown in table 1.

Research Question Two: What is the fitness of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique when used as office wears by female University staff in Northwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Responses on the fitness of clothing accessories: Beading, Crochet and Macramé items used as corporate dressing (Hand bags, shoes, necklace, earrings and watchstraps).

S/N	Required Observation	MCA (%)	
		Yes	No
1	Clothing accessories hangs well on the wearer when used. (hand bags, neck laces and ear rings)	143 (95.3)	7 (4.7)
2	Clothing accessories are attractive on the wearer. (hand bags, neck lace, ear rings, shoes and watch straps)	148 (98.7)	2 (1.3)
3	Clothing accessories looks elegant when worn (hand bags, neck lace, ear rings, shoes and watch straps)	129 (86)	21 (14)
4	Clothing accessories looks corporate on the body when worn (shoes, hand bags, neck lace, ear rings and watch straps)	125 (83.3)	25 (16.7)
Grand Mean (percentage)		136.2 (90.8)	13.8 (9.2)

Clothing accessories produced using macramé techniques when used as office wears by the University staff were fitting on the wearer as the total mean score and percentage of 136.2 and 90.8 percent respectively as shown in table 2.

Research Question Three: What is the level of acceptance of the clothing accessories produced using macramé technique as office wears by female University staff in Northeast, Nigeria?

Table 3: Respondents on Acceptability of Clothing accessories: Macramé technique as office wears (Hand bags, shoes, necklace, earrings and watchstraps)

S/N	Required Observation	MCA (%)	
		Yes	No
1	Clothing accessories are well accepted for corporate dressing in terms of the aesthetics.	128 (85.3)	22 (14.7)
2	The qualities of materials used for production of clothing accessories are accepted.	134 (89.3)	16 (10.7)
3	All clothing accessories were accepted for use for general wears because of their functionality.	132 (88)	18 (12)
Mean (percentage)		131.3 (87.5)	18.7 (12.5)

Clothing accessories produced using macramé techniques were accepted for used as office wears by University staff in Northeast, Nigeria as the total mean score and percentages of 131.3 and 87.5 percent respectively as shown in table 3. The

clothing accessories (tote bags, slippers, necklace, earrings, and watchstraps) were fitting and attractive on the wearer and suitable for use as office wears and as such a grand mean score of 131.3 was obtained which was 87.5 percent.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) produced using macramé were found to be comfortable, light in weight and without pains or aches during use with no irritation to the skin. This concurs with the findings of Frisna (2024) who observed that macrame and beaded clothing accessories are durable, resilient and can handle exposure to different weather.

Furthermore, the study showed that clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) produced using macramé techniques were found to be fitted on the wearer when used as office wears, this is inline with Jonathan (2016) who stated that accessories add colour, style and class to one's outfit and create certain look which may be practical and functional. He added that, accessories has a way of enhancing one's appearance, look and aesthetic.

The study showed clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) produced using macramé techniques were accepted for use by the wearers for office wears, this finding is in agreement with Olabisi (2021) who found positive results regarding the acceptability and marketability of the designs and the techniques of handcrafted macrame.

The findings of this study also revealed that the uniqueness and classic look of all the clothing Accessories (bags, shoes, necklace, earrings and watchstraps) produced using macramé techniques for use as office wears as stated by the researchers in the earlier chapter and to re-introduce the crafts that are going into extinction were accepted by the female University staff in Northeast Nigeria. This was reflected in the mean scores and percentages of research question (3) three in table 3, which showed that the clothing accessories produced using macramé techniques were accepted as office wears by University staff in Northeast Nigeria which was 131.3 mean score and 87.5 percent. This suggests that if these clothing accessories are made available, they will be accepted for use by the University staff in Northeast Nigeria. Hubpage, (2021); stated that accessories has the ability to change the way one looks even when wearing the same apparel, which also agrees with Jonathan, (2016) which stated that; accessories also add colour, style and class to one's outfit and create certain look which may be practical and functional. Jonathan (2016) also concluded that these accessories especially beads ornaments has a way of enhancing one's appearance, look and aesthetic.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, these clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) were found to be more comfortable, All the clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) were accepted as fitted, light, soft and were not painful, no aches or irritation on the skin during use, likewise the selected techniques for all the clothing accessories (tote bags, neck lace, ear rings, slippers, and watch straps) acceptable by the female University staff for use as corporate dressing.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Female university staff should be encouraged to use macramé clothing accessories since they are comfortable during use.

2. Female university staff should be encouraged to use macramé clothing accessories since it was observed that they were fitting on the wearer.
3. Clothing accessories made using macrame should be made available for use since it was observed that they were acceptable by the female university staff.

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